

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF USING OUTDOOR GAMES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING HANDBALL TO GIRLS AGED 10-11 YEARS

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Annotation. The article discusses the problems of developing accuracy in children of senior preschool age in the process of conducting handball classes using outdoor games. It is noted that games with elements of sports are one of the effective means of physical improvement, the formation of motor skills and abilities in preschool children, as well as motor abilities, in particular accuracy. The motor ability of precision is characterized as the ability to hit the target during any manipulation of an object.

Key words: accuracy, handball game, outdoor games, schoolchildren; level of development of accuracy, system of work.

Introduction. In the first school years of life, physical education is the basis for the comprehensive development of a child. During this period, the foundation of health, normal physical development is laid, and the basic personality traits of a person are developed [3, 5]. Physical education is carried out mainly in collective forms of work.

At school age, collective games using a ball play an important role [1, 2]. By playing such games, schoolchildren actively develop moral as well as physical qualities and abilities, in particular accuracy [4, 7, 8].

Today, the issue of developing accuracy in school-age children through the use of ball games is quite relevant, because more and more school education institutions are introducing sports games such as basketball, football, handball [6, 9]. These games help improve health, increase the level of motor training, and comprehensive

development of physical qualities of schoolchildren. The use of elements of sports games at school age lays the foundation for the child to systematically practice one of the sports in subsequent years.

Recently, the level of physical fitness of the younger generation has noticeably decreased, which negatively affects the effectiveness of educational, professional, military and other types of youth activities [10, 11]. The physical fitness of school-age children is of particular concern. One of the important tasks of physical education is the development of motor function and the ability to control one's movements.

School age is a favorable period for the development and improvement of motor and coordination abilities and skills. At school age, children experience rapid growth, active improvement of body functions, and a sensitive period begins for the development of physical qualities, skills, and abilities, among which accuracy takes the leading place. At school age, the foundations of a movement culture are laid, previously unknown exercises are successfully mastered, and new motor skills are formed [12, 13]. Many indicators of a child's motor abilities demonstrate high growth rates. The most intense increase is observed in indicators of coordination of movements, flexibility, and balance function [14].

At school age, a child experiences changes in all body systems; this age is most favorable for the formation in children of almost all physical qualities and coordination abilities, realized in physical activity. Currently, the foundation is being laid for the development of coordination abilities, as well as the acquisition of knowledge, skills and abilities in the process of performing coordination exercises. The game form of organizing children's motor activity as a stimulator of emotional saturation forms the motivation for active participation, ensures a sufficient level of activity and quality of performance of motor actions. The fact that games with handball elements are mainly played in the fresh air doubles the healing effect on the child's body. All this emphasizes the importance and expediency of using games with sports elements in the process of physical education of school-age children.

According to scientists, games with elements of sports are one of the effective means of physical improvement and the formation of skills and abilities in school-age children. An analysis of scientific sources convincingly shows that mainly local scientific research was carried out within the framework of the relevant games. In particular, the works of E. Adashkevicienė reveal the content and methodology of teaching handball.

A. Kurok and E. Vilchkovsky determine the content and methodology of conducting classes with elements of handball in school institutions. The problem of studying the use of sports games has been studied by many scientists. At school age, children are physically and mentally developed enough to play games with elements of sports. It is advisable to more widely use games that promote the development of the child's perception of his body movements and body positions, differentiation of muscle sensations, because on this basis, children develop the ability to control motor actions. For this purpose, it is advisable to offer children to perform exercises with a specific motor task (target setting), to accurately follow the direction, amplitude, speed and magnitude of muscle efforts.

For example, throwing objects while trying to hit a target. This makes it possible to "feel" the movements the first time you perform them, and then repeat them in the same way with a change in the target setting (for example, the landing location in depth jumps changes). The value of such exercises is that the conditions for their implementation constantly vary, which determines the formation of plastic skills and its greater adaptation to changing circumstances.

Of course, sports and outdoor games are an effective means of developing accuracy in school-age children. The study of the problem of teaching school-age children elements of sports games in the physical education of schoolchildren and the definition of their methodological foundations belong to E. Adashkyavichene, A. Boginich, Y. Babachuk, E. Vilchkovsky, L. Voloshina.

O. Konokh proposed her own program for the integrated use of sports games (mini-futsal, mini-basketball, mini-handball) for children 8-10 years old, which helps

improve the physical condition and increase the efficiency of the physical education process for school-age children.

Researcher L. Voloshina substantiated the possibilities of developing motor abilities of schoolchildren in the process of physical education through the targeted use of games with elements of sports. G. Chepurkina's research has proven the effectiveness of using mini-handball elements with school-age children.

A. Boginich, Yu. Babachuk determined the levels of complexity of game tasks: adaptive-developmental, preparatory-technical and active-game based on the use of elements of sports games aimed at the consistent acquisition of technical game techniques by school-age children.

An essential feature of sports games is the complex nature of the impact on the child's body (formation and improvement of motor skills, development of physical qualities and body functions), as well as the development of moral and volitional qualities.

Accuracy is the ability to hit the target during any manipulation of an object. For schoolchildren, accuracy can be determined by throwing a ball at a target, hitting it at the goal or rolling it, throwing bags.

You can develop accuracy through outdoor games, ball games and sports games. Accuracy is closely related to the eye. An eye meter is a child's ability to determine the distance to an object without special instruments. Also important prerequisites for the development of accuracy are spatial orientation and coordination of movements, the ability to coordinate one's movements with the tasks assigned to the child.

Accuracy has the following main components:

- taking a pose;
- aiming;
- adjusting breathing and other vegetative systems;
- performing the final effort.

Adopting a pose ensures a stable body position and creates favorable opportunities for conditioned reflex changes in many autonomic functions. The correct distribution of support points in the adopted position allows the child to perform the necessary movement correctly and as best as possible.

Aiming is the next component of accuracy. Its peculiarity is the combination of the maximum degree of concentration of excitation in the cerebral cortex with developed differentiated inhibition. The success of aiming is determined by the conditions of the task and the child's readiness. Hitting a given target is ensured by the optimal combination of throwing force, the flight trajectory of the object, and the consistency and accuracy of motor actions.

Orientation in space is the child's ability to correctly understand the meaning of prepositions, distinguish between the direction of movement and sides. Coordination is the process of coordinating the activity of the muscles of the body, aimed at the successful completion of a motor task, that is, the ability to carry out precise, targeted movements. It is advisable to develop all these characteristics of a child's physical development while playing with a ball, because no matter how the ball will help the child to develop comprehensively.

The most effective form of teaching schoolchildren to play sports is specially organized classes and walks. Sports games and exercises are aimed primarily at strengthening health, improving the physical fitness of children, and satisfying their biological need for movement.

In sports games, children acquire the correct skills, meeting the general technical needs of sports games, which eliminates relearning in the future and is important for preparing for school. To introduce children to sports games, fluent ball skills are important. Actions with the ball contribute to the formation of the necessary skills - to catch, catch and hold, throw the ball, determining the direction of the throw, its strength, the ability to correctly navigate in space.

In order for the game of handball to be successful and effective, you need to practice throwing the ball into the goal and passing it from one player to another. Without

developing accuracy, there will be no accurate throw. And without an accurate shot into the goal, there will be no victories for the team. Therefore, it is advisable, before playing handball, to play games to develop accuracy and eye. If we talk about the individual characteristics of children in mastering actions with a ball, it is worth noting that there are schoolchildren for whom these actions are easy, and there are children for whom the opposite is true.

Children who have more coordinated and accurate movements, who react faster to signals, and are able to assess the situation on the court, quickly master the correct technique of handling the ball. It is enough for them to show, explain and give them the opportunity to practice the actions, and after 2-3 lessons the children will be able to perform the basic movements of the game. In the process of further exercises, these children will be able not only to perform such game moments as throwing the ball into the goal and passing it, but also to move correctly around the playground and evaluate their position on it.

Conclusions. So, after analyzing the psychological, pedagogical and methodological literature, it was established that the problem of developing accuracy in school-age children through outdoor games is relevant and important. The influence of sports and outdoor games on the development of accuracy in school-age children has been substantiated. To improve the level of development of accuracy in children, a system of work with the active use of sports and outdoor games was developed. When choosing a game, you need to determine the purpose of the game, take into account the age and individual characteristics of children and their physical fitness. Also, when selecting games, pay special attention to ensuring that the themes of the games coincide with games for the development of accuracy.

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